

EDUCATIONAL HERALD

(A QUARTERLY JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH)

Jan. - March 2011

Vol. 40

No. 1

One Who Dares To Teach Must Never Cease To Learn

SHAH GOVERDHANLAL KABRA TEACHERS' COLLEGE (C.T.E.), JODHPUR
Accredited with B⁺⁺ by NAAC - U.G.C.

Contents

1. Editorial.....	3
2. Effective Use of PowerPoint in Lectures	5
– Prof N.N. Pandey	
– Pratibha Sagar	
3. Personality Needs of Hearing Impaired Children Having High and Low Aspiration	13
– Monika Saroj	
– Dr. Usha Mishra	
4. Quality of Education in the Formal Systems to Develop an Empowered Society.....	22
– Dr. Doongar Singh Kheechee	
5. Influence of Study Habits, Food Habits And T.V. Viewing on Academic Achievement of School Students	28
– Dr. Latika Sharma	
– Anuradha	
6. Application of ICT in Teacher Education.....	36
– Dr. [Miss] Prabhjotkaur	
7. A Study—Important Mode of Communication for Teacher Empowerment.....	44
– Mr. Yatendrakumar S. Pal	
8. A Study of Emotional Intelligence Among Adolescents in Relation to Intelligence and Formal Reasoning.....	48
– Ruchi Dubey	
9. Technology in ELT.....	57
– Dr. Sunita Jakhar	

Effective Use of PowerPoint in Lectures

Prof N.N. Pandey¹

Pratibha Sagar²

Changes are taking place in our society at an exponential rate. The usability of technology has put a new spin on education, redefining the role of educators and reshaping classroom learning experiences. The ability to use technology opens new opportunities to explore ways to teach and learn. The concept of using technology in learning is not new; the format of the technology is also changing. Technologies, ranging from books to slide rules, calculators, televisions and computers, have supplemented teaching-learning for years. Changes in technology have been at a non-linear rate and now provide new options to deliver more effective, personalized instruction than it was in the past. Today's generation is growing up with a different expectation of technology's role in their lives.

In the student-centered classrooms of today, with the aid of computers, students are able to collaborate, to use critical thinking, and to find alternatives to solutions of problems. Student-centered teaching is challenging educators to restudy their teaching methods and student learning methods (Jaber, 1997). Research done by Dwyer *et al.* (1991) indicates that computers can be used in collaboration for all subject areas, but that teachers have to take into account the different styles of teaching and the students involved in this learning. This type of teaching requires a change in pedagogy, the amount of time needed to learn how to use the technology and the location of models that work with technology (Sheingold and Hadley, 1990).

The dominant teaching method in Universities is lecturing. It is used by most of the teachers in higher education as their principal teaching strategy. The format is simple and straightforward: the teacher presents

¹ Professor, Faculty of Education and Allied Sciences, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly.

² Assistant Professor, Faculty of Education and Allied Sciences, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly.

(and illustrates, demonstrates, etc.) large amount of information to large audience in limited time. It gives the teacher total control of content, pace, organization and direction. Johnson *et al.* (1998) identified six specific pedagogical problems associated with lecturing as:

- Students' attention to what the lecturer is saying decreases as the lecture proceeds.
- For a lecture to be effective it takes an educated, intelligent person oriented towards an auditory learning style.
- Lecturing tends to promote only lower level learning of factual information
- Lecturing is limited by the assumption that all students need the same information presented orally at the same time and at the same pace, without dialogue with the presenter, and in an impersonal way.
- Students tend not to like lecturing
- Lecturing is based upon a series of assumptions about the cognitive capabilities and strategies of students.

It is clear that the simple transmission of information through a lecture is not an effective approach for meeting the goals of helping students become independent, critical problem solvers, able to interact with their peers in social and employment situations. Aside from threats of obsolescence, pedagogically lecturing is a flawed approach to teaching and needs to be replaced by more effective teaching paradigms. One of the approaches for replacing lectures with information delivered by computers is in form of PowerPoint presentations.

PowerPoint is an integral component within the suite of programs known collectively as Microsoft Office. PowerPoint (© Microsoft Corp.) is a widely used presentation programme that originated in the world of business but has now become common place in the world of educational technology. It provides a complete set of resources for creating presentations. PowerPoint is, just like the name says, a powerful tool for teaching and learning. It is basically variety of electronic slides where a person can embed files such as texts, music, pictures, diagram, or whatever else one likes. Its benefit is that students are engaged not just through words, but also through visuals. Some students learn better by hearing, but

other students learn better by seeing. Also, it provides for some excitement in that it breaks down the daily routine of lectures.

PowerPoint is a user-friendly package that can be used for the creation of visually clear, dynamic and attention capturing presentations (Holzl, 1997). Its adoption compels the speaker into a well-organized path on which the most important points are emphasized (Harknett and Cobane, 1997). Its use in education has been already pioneered at many Universities and colleges around the world. Lecturers are warned, however, that their true challenge is to use PowerPoint and IT in general, for the enrichment of students' learning rather than simply for improvement and/or modernization of their performances in the classroom (Sipress, 1995).

Basically, the teaching strategy used in higher education is usually based on average learner. The attention could not be paid on individual learner. Proper and structured presentation of lectures is the only solution to solve all these problems. The question that we are now dealing with is how to most effectively utilize presentation technology as we teach students. One of the most prevalent types of technology being used in the classroom is different types of presentation software. Microsoft PowerPoint, for example, is a popular choice of lecture aids.

PowerPoint can be a tool for guiding students in note-taking, reinforcing points made in a lecture, and to inject occasional humour or visual reinforcement. PowerPoint's design and expected use, adds to the didactic nature of classroom teaching where there is already too much of: teacher-centered, pre planned, lockstep delivery of information, given primarily through words (Mason & Hlynka, 1998).

The use of PowerPoint in education stems directly from one of its most favourable features, namely the ease of use. This has resulted in, often questionable, practices within educational contexts. It particularly includes poorly thought-out use in lectures where it becomes simply an alternative form of presenting largely text-based material that used to be delivered using 'old technology' (chalk and talk): this makes little use of the new and flexible opportunities offered by use of PowerPoint within the educational field.

The genius of Microsoft is that they do facilitate us in using this great tool by making it so easy to take advantage of all of PowerPoint's fantastic tools. In a classroom setting, PowerPoint alone could represent one of the biggest revolutions in how to present information to students in a long

time. But it's a good idea to think through how to use the tool and have some ground rules for how to use it so that one gets the maximum value from PowerPoint without becoming abusive of its powers. PowerPoint presentations enable teachers to increase the quality of written material and visuals they present to the students in the class. The alternatives to PowerPoint presentations are using blackboard/whiteboard, and charts. Though to completely eliminate the use of blackboard, the PowerPoint offers some distinct advantages. First the PowerPoint presentations can be made in advance, thereby effectively increasing the time available to the teacher to teach. Also the PowerPoint makes it possible to provide a much richer quality of visuals including multicoloured complicated diagrams and pictures.

Effective PowerPoint presentations attempts to keep the audience attention focused on the subject material and away from distractions. However, the attention will lag if insufficient assimilation time is provided to the audience. The speed that the presenter uses in the lecture should not be too quick, especially if the topic is difficult to comprehend. Power Point has the words and pictures ready, and "speed presenting" can be a problem, especially if the topic is exciting to the lecturer. The presenter should try to go a bit slower instead of a bit faster whenever possible. The audience learning retention rate will be greater in these cases when the pace of the presentation is slowed down.

Reasons to use PowerPoint

There are many reasons to use PowerPoint in teaching learning process but the key ones include :

- Appropriate use of PowerPoint can enhance the teaching and learning experience for teachers and students.
- It provides encouragement and support to teacher by facilitating the structuring of a presentation in a professional manner. The templates provided have been designed to default to good presentation criteria such as the number of lines of information per slide and appropriate font sizes and types, etc: using the styles of the default templates can significantly improve the clarity and structuring of a presentation. This helps to avoid the common use of excessive text often found on overhead transparencies.

- By careful mixing of media, a presentation can appeal to a number of different learning styles and be made more stimulating. Teachers are encouraged to incorporate more sophisticated visual and auditory media into presentations although care is required because of the inevitable increase in file sizes and the danger of excessive use.
- The electronic file format allows distribution and modification for/by students unable to be present or who have impaired visual or auditory difficulties
- Editing of each PowerPoint file is very easy with minimal associated reprinting costs.
- The printing of handouts in a variety of formats is facilitated with a number of embedded options to print either the slides themselves (useful if there are graphics involved) or the text from the slides (outlines).
- Extra information can be 'hidden' within files for answering predicted questions. The use of speakers notes as an automated feedback system was described by (Mottley, 2003) who also describes other ways to use PowerPoint for development of self-study materials.
- The portability of the files, especially on compact disks (CDs) and pen drives/flash drives with their large capacity, allows presentations to be given wherever the technology is available. Presentations can also be set up to run automatically if required.

Creating a successful presentation

There are diverse teaching and learning contexts in which PowerPoint can be used for presentations but the key general requirements are summarized below.

- Plan the presentation structure carefully and according to the general rules of presentations. The key to a successful presentation/lecture is to have a clear structure and generally not more than five key topic areas.
- Know the level at which the presentation is aimed and develop the content for this level

- Do not present too much textual material on each slide and avoid simply reading out what is on the slide: provide mainly structural headings and sub-headings around which the bulk of the verbal presentation takes place so that students still require being active and taking notes of detail, etc
- Use a single readable font of size greater than 24 points for most of the presentation. Font of different colours, sizes and styles (bold, underline) are preferred for impact.
- Keep the background consistent and subtle. Use dark text on light background or light text on dark background. Content presented on slides must not be in all caps except for titles or occasional emphasis – they are harder to read than lower-case letters.
- Do not use more than two text colours in a presentation unless there are particular reasons for doing so.
- Consider introducing lines of text one at a time, dimming the previous lines as the new line is introduced: this facilitates concentration on the current item. Putting the full slide up can result in the audience reading ahead and not listening to what is being currently discussed. This facility is accessed within the custom animation option.
- Use quality clipart and use it sparingly. The graphic should relate to and enhance the topic of the slide. Avoid flashy graphics and noisy animation effects unless they relate directly to the slide.
- Limit the number of transitions used. It is often better to use only one so the audience knows what to expect.
- Make sure to speak at a normal pace and do not allow the use of PowerPoint to deliver material too quickly: this is one of the most commonly encountered problems when converting to using PowerPoint.
- Do not read the presentation. Practice the presentation so you can speak from bullet points. The text should be a cue for the presenter rather than a message for the viewer.

- It is often more effective to have bulleted points appear one at a time so the audience listens to the presenter rather than reading the screen.
- Utilize the visual and other media opportunities offered to enhance the presentation whenever possible but be careful to avoid excessive use of colour effects, animation effects, transition effects, sound effects, etc.
- Do not turn your back on the audience. Try to position the monitor so you can speak from it.

Conclusions

PowerPoint is an excellent aid to presentations providing each presentation is considered first from a pedagogical viewpoint, bearing in mind the different ways in which students learn and largely trying to avoid the pitfalls of passive knowledge transmission. When PowerPoint is used appropriately, it does encourage the teachers, for the sake of a relatively shallow learning-curve, to improve the professionalism and quality of their didactic sessions and facilitates the development and evolution of more interactive and flexible practices – PowerPoint is much more powerful and flexible than that and alternative activities can be facilitated by its use,

References

- *Dwyer, D. (1994). Apple classrooms of tomorrow: What we've learned. Retrieved on 24 Feb 2002. Available : <http://www.ascd.org/readingroom/edlead/9404/dwyer.html>*
- *Harknett, R.J., and Cobane, C.T. (1997). Introducing instructional technology to international relations. Political Science and Politics, 30, 496-500.*
- *Holzl, J. (1997). Twelve tips for effective PowerPoint presentation for the technologically challenged. Medical Teacher, 19, 175-179.*
- *Jaber, William (1997). A survey of factors which influence teachers' use of computer based technology. Dissertation Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University.*
- *Johnson, D.W., Johnson, R.T., Smith, K.A., (1998). Problems with lecturing. Cooperative Learning and College Teaching, 9(1), 2-3*

- *Mason, R. & Hlynka, D. (1998) Power Point in the classroom: Where is the power? Educational Technology, 38, pp. 45-48.*
- *Mottley, J. (2003) Developing self-study materials with PowerPoint. LTSN Bioscience Bulletin, 9, Summer 2003, p9.*
- *Sheingold, K., and Hadley, M. (1990). Accomplished teachers: Integrating computers into classroom practice. New York: Bank Street College of Education.*
- *Sipress, M. (1995). Computer software in the undergraduate political science classroom. Paper presented at the 1995 Annual meeting of American Political Science Association in Chicago, ILL.*

SHRI MAHESH SHIKSHAN SANSTHAN, JODHPUR

Book-Post

Printed-Book

To,

If undelivered, please return to :

Principal,
S. G. K. Teacher's College,
Near Gita Bhawan, Jodhpur - 342 003 INDIA

